

Effect of Liquid on the Magnetic Force Microscope Imaging

Jinyun Liu^{1,2}, Zhengxun Song¹ and Zuobin Wang^{1,2*}

¹CNM & JR3CN

Changchun University of Science and Technology
Changchun, China
wangz@cust.edu.cn

Renxi Qiu² and Dayou Li^{2*}

²IRAC & JR3CN

University of Bedfordshire,
Luton, UK
dayou.li@beds.ac.uk

Abstract—It is known that when the probe vibrating in liquid, the oscillation of the cantilever is significantly damped by the interaction forces between the water molecular and the probe surface, which is known as the hydration force. Thus, the parameters of a tapping magnetic probe are significantly affected. In this work, the resonant frequency, Q-factor and spring constant of the magnetic probe in air and liquid environments were analyzed. The MFM images of a hard disk acquired in ambient and liquid conditions were compared. It was found that the hydration force significantly affected the parameters of the magnetic probe and then the quality of the MFM images was significantly decreased. To improve the quality of the magnetic images, the drive amplitude and the lift height were adjusted. The results showed that the magnetic features were recognized with the increases of the drive amplitude and the appropriate lift height.

Keywords; *Magnetic force microscope (MFM); drive amplitude; lift height.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic force microscope (MFM) systems have been widely used for charactering the magnetic recordings by detecting the magnetic interaction forces between the magnetic probe and the sample with nano resolution [1], including the studies of the domain structures of nanocomposite [2], thickness of thin film [3] and manipulation of vortexes [4]. In an MFM, a magnetic tip is coated with a magnetized layer (Fe/Co/Cr), the phase shift and amplitude signals of cantilever are usually detected for the imaging of magnetic samples with high resolution in ambient conditions [5].

Due to the unique features including the high reactivity, high surface area and biocompatibility [6], some of the magnetic materials such as magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have been widely used in life sciences and investigated for cancer diagnosis and treatment [7, 8], drug delivery [9, 10] and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [11, 12]. Zou et al. [13] investigated the anticancer activity of doxorubicin-loaded magnetic nanoparticles (DOX-CMMN) on MCF-7 cells under an alternating current magnetic field (ACMF). The results indicated that DOX-CMMN could target the MCF-7 cells and control the release of drug under ACMF. Sadeghi et al. [14] studied the effects of Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles on the cytotoxicity of Hep G2 cells by incubation. The experiment results suggested that Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles could reduce the cell

viability and lead to the cell apoptosis. Venkatesha et al. [15] investigated the GO-Fe₃O₄ as a contrast agent in MRI and analyzed its cytotoxicity, and the results showed that the particles were biocompatible to normal cells, but they were toxic to breast cancer cells.

The applications of MNPs in biomedicine are broadly. However, the distributions of the MNPs and their effects on morphological features of cells are unclearly in the reports. To study of the effects of MNPs on biological samples and obtain the high resolution images of MNPs, there is the need for an MFM system working in liquid environments. Accordingly, the analysis of the effects of liquid on the magnetic imaging is essential.

In this work, the effects of liquid on MFM imaging were investigated, and the results were important for the application of the MFM in biomedicine.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mica with the size of 15 mm×15 mm×1 mm was used as the nonmagnetic sample and hard disk cut into 10 mm×10 mm were used as the magnetic sample. All the measurements were implemented by JPK (NanoWizard®3, Germany) MFM system. The magnetic probe (Magnetic Multi 75-G, Budgetsensors) was used for the imaging and measurement of the samples in air and liquid environments. The typical resonance frequency of the probe was 75 kHz, the spring constant was 3 N/m, the cantilever length was 225 μm and the tip height was 17 μm. The liquid used in the experiments was ultrapure water and the ambient environment was a standard clean room.

The parameters of the magnetic probe including the resonance frequency, quality factor, spring constant and separation energy were obtained on the substrate of mica and hard disk in ambient and water environments, and they were detected with a height of 30 μm from the hard disk and mica surface. Each group of the parameters were collected with at least 10 measurements, and the results were calculated as Mean±SD values.

III. THEORY

It is possible for an MFM to measure forces with different detecting techniques [16] and there are interaction forces

between the magnetic dipole moment of the tip and the sample. Because of its high sensitivity and stability, the common method used for detecting the force gradient is to calculate the phase shift of an oscillation cantilever [5].

The forces detected by MFM are purely magnetic static forces and they depend on the interactions of the magnetic dipole moment of the magnetic tip and the measured sample [17]. For the phase shift $\Delta\phi$ MFM imaging method, the phase signal of every point of the scanned area is recorded. The phase shift is proportional to the derivative of the force between the tip and the sample in the Z direction, it can be expressed as [3, 18]

$$\Delta\phi = QF'/k \quad (1)$$

where Q and k are the quality factor and the spring constant of the cantilever, respectively.

The magnetic force acting on a volume element dV' in the tip can be given by [19-21]

$$dF = \mu_0 \nabla(M(r') \cdot H(r+r')) dV' \quad (2)$$

where μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of free space, $M(r')$ is the magnetization of the volume element in the tip, and $H(r+r')$ is the stray field from the sample to the tip [17]. The tip can be simple to be a point probe with one magnetic element, then the magnetic force can be rewritten as [22]

$$F_m = \mu_0 \nabla(m \cdot H) \quad (3)$$

where m is the effective dipole moment of the tip.

F' is the magnetic force in the Z direction of the tip and it is detected by the cantilever of the probe. Thus, F' can be calculated by [21]

$$F' = dF/dz = \mu_0 m_z (\partial^2 H_z / \partial z^2) \quad (4)$$

where it is assumed that the tip is magnetized in the vertical direction and $m = \{0, 0, m_z\}^T$.

In liquid environments, the forces interacted on the probe are quite complex. However, compared to the ambient environment, the van der Waals forces are reduced significantly, and the capillary forces are eliminated and electrostatic forces are minimized [23-25]. For the working magnetic probe, the magnetic force F_M , drive force F_D , hydrate force F_H and noise force F_N are coexisted, as shown in Fig. 1.

The probe is fixed at one end on the probe holder, and the piezoelectric actuator is fixed on the probe holder and adjacent to the probe. A voltage signal is applied to the actuator to drive the cantilever oscillation. A uniform beam is used to measure the deflection of the probe cantilever. When the probe vibrating in the liquid, the oscillation of the cantilever is significantly damped by the interaction forces between the water molecules and the probe surface, which is known as the hydration force [26]. In an AFM system, the laser is detected by optical position sensitive detector (OPSD). The displacement sensor noise and thermal displacement are the two major noises consisting of the frequency noise [27]. Thus, the magnetic forces between the sample and the probe are

significantly affected in the liquid.

Fig. 1. Forces of magnetic probe on the magnetic sample in the liquid.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To improve the quality of the MFM images obtained in the liquid environment, the parameters of the magnetic probe in air and liquid environments are analyzed. The MFM images of a hard disk obtained in both ambient and liquid environments are compared.

The resonance frequency of the magnetic probe in ambient and water environments is shown in Fig. 2. The resonance frequency of the probe working in the ambient environment is 74.21 kHz and its amplitude is 1.52 V with the drive amplitude of 0.17 V, as shown in Fig. 2(a). With the same drive amplitude, the resonance frequency of the probe tapping in the water is 28.61 kHz and its amplitude is 0.08 V, as shown in Fig. 2(b). It is known that the amplitude is too low to scan the magnetic samples and acquire their magnetic features. The drive amplitude is increased to 1.90 V to improve the amplitude of the probe oscillating in the water, as shown in Fig. 2(c). Then the amplitude is raised to 1.50 V with the resonance frequency of 27.2 kHz. It can be seen that the resonance frequency and its amplitude are affected significantly by the liquid. The amplitude can be improved by the increase of the drive amplitude.

The resonant frequency of the magnetic probe in ambient and water environments is collected on the mica and hard disk substrate surfaces, as shown in Fig. 3. The resonant frequency on the mica surface and hard disk surface are similar in the ambient environment, and the values are 72.02 ± 0.01 kHz and 72.14 ± 0.01 kHz, respectively. In the water, the resonant frequencies are 28.76 ± 0.39 kHz and 28.72 ± 0.18 kHz, respectively. It can be concluded that there are insignificant effects of substrate on the resonant frequency due to the hydration force of the water, and the resonant frequency are reduced significantly in the water.

The Q-factor of the magnetic probe in ambient and water environments are shown in Fig. 4. In the ambient environment, for the mica sample the Q-factor is 192.48 ± 22.97 and for the disk sample the Q-factor is 165.07 ± 12.24 . In the water, the Q-factor on the mica surface is 3.66 ± 0.13 and on the hard disk surface is 3.68 ± 0.16 . It can be seen that the substrates have little effect on the Q-factor in the ambient environment but unaffected on it in the water environment. Because of the resistance of the water, the oscillation of the probe is significantly damped and the quality factor Q is reduced dramatically. Thus, the Q-factor in the air is larger than that in the liquid environment.

Fig. 2. Resonance frequency of the magnetic probe obtained in the ambient and water environments. (a) is obtained with a drive amplitude of 0.17V in the ambient environment. (b) is obtained with a drive amplitude of 0.17 V in the water and (c) is obtained with a drive amplitude of 1.90 V in the water.

The spring constants of the magnetic probe obtained in various environments are shown in Fig. 5. In the ambient environment, the spring constant is 3.40 ± 0.22 N/m for the mica substrate and it is 3.11 ± 0.25 N/m for the hard disk substrate. It can be seen that the magnetic field has little effect on the spring constant of the magnetic probe in the air. In the water, the spring constant on the mica surface is the same as that on the hard disk, and the substrate has no effect on the spring constant.

From Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it can be seen that the reduction of the Q from the air to water is larger than the decrease of k from the air to water. Thus, $(Q/k)_{\text{air}} > (Q/k)_{\text{water}}$. For the same F' , $\Delta\phi_{\text{air}} > \Delta\phi_{\text{water}}$, and the quality of MFM images is affected by liquid.

Fig. 3. Resonance frequency of the magnetic probe obtained in ambient and water environments.

Fig. 4. Q-factor of the magnetic probe obtained in the ambient and water environments.

Fig. 5. Spring constant of the magnetic probe obtained in ambient and water environments.

In Fig. 6, force-distance curves of the four groups are compared. It can be seen that the maximum adhesion forces (the lowest position of the curve) of the probe retracted from the disk and mica surfaces are significantly different in the ambient environment. It is because that there is a magnetic force (attractive/repulsive force) between the probe and the disk. However, due to the resistance of the liquid there are little differences between the disk and mica in the water environment. The retraction speed is $2.0 \mu\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 6. Force-distance curves of the magnetic probe in water and ambient environments.

The phase shift signals are used for the imaging of hard disk obtained in air and water environments, as shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 7(a) is obtained with the lift height of 50 nm and with the scan rate of 1.00 Hz, and the drive amplitude is 2.537 V in the air. It can be seen that the magnetic domain structures are clearly recognized in the air. Fig. 7 (b) is acquired with the lift height of 20 nm and the scan rate of 0.5 kHz, and the drive amplitude of 3.387 V in the water. The magnetic domain structures cannot be found. Fig. 7 (c) is observed with the lift

height of 20 nm and with the scan rate of 0.5 kHz, and the drive amplitude is increased to 4.511 V in the water. It can be seen that the magnetic domains can be observed with the increase of the drive amplitude in the liquid environment.

Fig. 7. MFM images of a hard disk obtained in the air and water. (a) MFM image of the hard disk obtained in the air with the drive amplitude of 2.537 V. (b) MFM image of the hard disk obtained in the water with the drive amplitude of 3.387 V. (c) MFM image of the hard disk obtained in the water with the drive amplitude of 4.511 V. The image size is 128×128 pixels.

The lift height significantly influences the MFM imaging in the liquid, as shown in Fig. 8. In the experiments, the scan rate is 0.60 Hz and the drive amplitude is 4.782 V. (a) is the topography image of the hard disk. (b) is obtained with the lift height of 10 nm. The topography significantly affects the MFM imaging, the topography characters are clearly as shown in the figure with arrows. (c) is acquired by the increase of the lift height to 20 nm and the effect of the topography is reduced with the magnetic features enhanced. (d) is obtained with the lift height of 50 nm and there is little topography effect but the magnetic features are weakened. It can be concluded that the lift heights affect topography and significantly influence the quality of the MFM images.

Fig. 8. MFM images of the hard disk acquired with different lift heights in the water. (a) Topography of the hard disk. (b) MFM image with the lift height of 10 nm. (c) MFM image with the lift height of 20 nm. (d) MFM image with the lift height of 50 nm. The arrows show the topography characters. The image size is 256×256 pixels.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the effect of liquid on the parameters of the magnetic probe was investigated. It is found that the resonant

frequency, amplitude, Q-factor and spring constant were reduced significantly in the liquid, and the MFM images were often with unclear magnetic features. To improve the quality of the magnetic images, the drive amplitude and the lift height should be adjusted. The results have shown that the magnetic features can be recognized with the increase of the drive amplitude and the appropriate lift height.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the “111” Project of China (D17017), National Key Basic Research Program of China (973 Program No.2012CB326406), EU FP7 (BioRA No.612641), China-EU H2020 (FabSurfWAR Nos.2016YFE0112100 and 644971), EU H2020 (MNR4SCell No.734174), National Natural Science Foundation Program of China (Nos.61176002, 11103047 and 11504030), and Jilin Provincial Science and Technology Program (Nos.20160520101JH, 20160101318JC and 20160623002TC).

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Wakaya, M. Kajiwara, K. Kubo, S. Abo, M. Takai, Improvement of current sensitivity in detecting current-induced magnetic field using magnetic force microscopy, *Microelec. Eng.* 88 (2011) 2778-2780.
- [2] W. Szmaja, J. Grobelny, M. Cichomski, S. Hiroswawa, Y. Shigemoto, Magnetic force microscopy investigation of the domain structure of nanocomposite Nd₂Fe₁₄B/Fe₃B magnets, *Acta Mater.* 59 (2011) 531-536.
- [3] D. Passeri, C. Dong, L. Angeloni, F. Pantanella, T. Natalizi, F. Berlutti, C. Marianecchi, F. Ciccarello, M. Rossi, Thickness measurement of soft thin films on periodically patterned magnetic substrates by phase difference magnetic force microscopy, *Ultramicroscopy* 136 (2014) 96-106.
- [4] E.H. Brandt, G.P. Mikitik, E. Zeldov, Deforming and moving a vortex by the tip of a magnetic force microscope, *Physica C: Superconductivity* 470 (2010) 782-785.
- [5] A. Alekseev, A. Popkov, A. Shubin, F. Pudonin, N. Djuzhev, Effect of horizontal magnetization reversal of the tips on magnetic force microscopy images, *Ultramicroscopy* 136 (2014) 91-95.
- [6] A. Akbarzadeh, M. Samiei, S. Davaran, Magnetic nanoparticles: preparation, physical properties, and applications in biomedicine, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 7 (2012) 144.
- [7] H.J. Hathaway, K.S. Butler, N.L. Adolphi, D.M. Lovato, R. Belfon, D. Fegan, T.C. Monson, J.E. Trujillo, T.E. Tessier, H.C. Bryant, D.L. Huber, R.S. Larson, E.R. Flynn, Detection of breast cancer cells using targeted magnetic nanoparticles and ultra-sensitive magnetic field sensors, *Breast Cancer Res.* 13 (2011) R108.
- [8] Y. Cheng, R.A. Morshed, B. Auffinger, A.L. Tobias, M.S. Lesniak, Multifunctional nanoparticles for brain tumor imaging and therapy, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 66 (2014) 42-57.
- [9] N.K. Verma, K. Crosbie-Staunton, A. Satti, S. Gallagher, K.B. Ryan, T. Doody, C. McAtamney, R. MacLoughlin, P. Galvin, C.S. Burke, Y. Volkov, Y.K. Gun'ko, Magnetic core-shell nanoparticles for drug delivery by nebulization, *Journal of Nanobiotechnology* 11 (2013) 12.
- [10] A. Latorre, P. Couleaud, A. Aires, A.L. Cortajarena, A. Somoza, Multifunctionalization of magnetic nanoparticles for controlled drug release: a general approach, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 82 (2014) 355-362.
- [11] F. Mouffouk, T. Simão, D.F. Dornelles, A.D. Lopes, P. Sau, J. Martins, K.M. Abu-Salah, S.A. Alrokayan, A.M. Rosa da Costa, N.R. dos Santos, Self-assembled polymeric nanoparticles as new, smart contrast agents for cancer early detection using magnetic resonance imaging, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 10 (2015) 63-76.
- [12] M. Iv, N. Telischak, D. Feng, S.J. Holdsworth, K.W. Yeom, H.E. Daldrup-Link, Clinical applications of iron oxide nanoparticles for magnetic resonance imaging of brain tumors, *Nanomedicine* 10 (2015) 993-1018.

- [13] Y. Zou, P. Liu, C.H. Liu, X.T. Zhi, Doxorubicin-loaded mesoporous magnetic nanoparticles to induce apoptosis in breast cancer cells, *Biomed Pharmacother* 69 (2015) 355-360.
- [14] J. Mosafer, K. Abnous, M. Tafaghodi, A. Mokhtarzadeh, M. Ramezani, In vitro and in vivo evaluation of anti-nucleolin-targeted magnetic PLGA nanoparticles loaded with doxorubicin as a theranostic agent for enhanced targeted cancer imaging and therapy, *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 113 (2017) 60-74.
- [15] N. Venkatesha, P. Poojar, Y. Qurishi, S. Geethanath, C. Srivastava, Graphene oxide-Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle composite with high transverse proton relaxivity value for magnetic resonance imaging, *Journal of Applied Physics* 117 (2015) 154702.
- [16] D. Rugar, H.J. Mamin, P. Guethner, S.E. Lambert, J.E. Stern, I. McFadyen, T. Yogi, Magnetic force microscopy: General principles and application to longitudinal recording media, *J. Appl. Phys.* 68 (1990) 1169.
- [17] P. Grütter, Applications of Magnetic Force Microscopy, *Forces in Scanning Probe Methods* (1995) 447-470.
- [18] S. Takaya, T. Suzuki, Y. Matsumoto, K. Demachi, M. Uesaka, Estimation of stress corrosion cracking sensitivity of type 304 stainless steel by magnetic force microscope, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 327 (2004) 19-26.
- [19] P. Grütter, D. Rugar, H.J. Mamin, Magnetic force microscopy of magnetic materials, *Ultramicroscopy* 47 (1992) 393-399.
- [20] R. Engel-Herbert, D.M. Schaadt, T. Hesjedal, Analytical and numerical calculations of the magnetic force microscopy response: A comparison, *J. Appl. Phys.* 99 (2006) 113905.
- [21] D. Baronov, S.B. Andersson, Tracking a magnetic nanoparticle in 3-D with a magnetic force microscope, In *Proceedings of the 47th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC) Cancun, Mexico* (2008) pp 5170-5175.
- [22] D. Baronov, S.B. Andersson, Controlling a magnetic force microscope to track a magnetized nanosize particle, *IEEE T. Nanotechnol.* 9 (2010) 367-374.
- [23] B. Kumar, P.M. Pifer, A. Giovengo, J. Legleiter, The effect of set point ratio and surface Young's modulus on maximum tapping forces in fluid tapping mode atomic force microscopy, *Journal of Applied Physics* 107 (2010) 044508.
- [24] G.Y. Chen, Transient response of tapping scanning force microscopy in liquids, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 14 (1996) 1313.
- [25] B.J. Rodriguez, S. Jesse, A.P. Baddorf, S.V. Kalinin, High resolution electromechanical imaging of ferroelectric materials in a liquid environment by piezoresponse force microscopy, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 96 (2006) 237602.
- [26] J.E. Sader, Frequency response of cantilever beams immersed in viscous fluids with applications to the atomic force microscope, *Journal of Applied Physics* 84 (1998) 64-76.
- [27] K. Kobayashi, H. Yamada, K. Matsushige, Frequency noise in frequency modulation atomic force microscopy, *Rev Sci Instrum* 80 (2009) 043708.